

THE PEDAGOGICAL CONDITION OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Ibraimova Gulmira Askarovna

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute pedagogic department 1st head doctoral student.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728966>

Abstract. This article covers the great importance attached to modern methods of teaching foreign languages in the process of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the modern teaching methods needed to organize them.

Key words: Foreign language in preschool education, Finnish teaching system, method of sign and picture, method of sound recognition and adaptation, method of organization with the natural world, method of adapting low activity to students.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ЮНЫМ ШКОЛЬНИКАМ.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещено большое значение, придаваемое современным методам обучения иностранным языкам в процессе дошкольного образования в Республике Узбекистан, а также современным методам обучения, необходимым для их организации.

Ключевые слова: Иностранный язык в дошкольном образовании, финская система обучения, метод жестов и изображений, метод распознавания и адаптации звуков, метод организации с миром природы, метод адаптации малоактивных учащихся.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first classes of general education schools from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of continuous training is proof of this.

Nowadays, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students of M.T.M. and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development.

Language learning also depends on age periods. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible.

The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way:

- to teach by means of songs and poems the letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember, that do not have meaning.

For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

- games related to mental and physical activities;

- cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters.

This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: a student howls a dog, meows a cat

shows, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first classes of general education schools from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of continuous training is proof of this.

Nowadays, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students of M.T.M. and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development.

Language learning also depends on age periods. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible.

The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way:

- to teach by means of songs and poems the letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember, that do not have meaning.

For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

- games related to mental and physical activities;

- cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters.

This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: a student howls a dog, meows a cat

shows, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

- subject environment; If the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, the children will learn the language better. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) This will strengthen the students' vocabulary, language skills, and develop their worldview.

- riddles; Children have a strong interest in finding answers to riddles. Therefore, when the teacher tells the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to answer it in English.

Then children learn words quickly.

- practical activities (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "The pedagogue, who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory, should use as many of the child's sensory organs as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations, and even if possible, he should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering".

For example: when a teacher tastes an apple, its color is red or green, He should give information about the smell of whether it is sweet (tasty) or sour () or fragrant () and by feeding the fruits to other students, he should ask the children to give information about that fruit in English. it also helps in further learning. If the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the time when he ate the fruit, he quickly remembers that it is red-red and green-green. Therefore, using such a method helps the student's ensures that information is kept in memory for a long time.

- through gestures, facial expressions; When the teacher says something to the child or gives an order, for example, if he uses gestures in sentences such as "come here", "open the book", "stand up", "look at the blackboard" will be clear.

- through visual aids, posters, books;

- things that are visible and often used in everyday life, objects

to write For example: door, book, table, blackboard,

write to window and so on. Since such things are always visible and often used in practice, the child learns these words involuntarily.

- through news; We know that children are curious. They quickly get bored with the sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them not always using the same methods, but to change and update such methods. Otherwise, children will understand how the teacher will teach and prepare for it. Teaching with innovative methods raises children's aspirations.

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should be conducted as an interesting activity and not as a duty. Learning using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. It is necessary to explain to children how important it is to learn foreign languages through natural conditions. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi knew many

foreign languages perfectly, was able to speak them easily and created in them. Such an opportunity motivated scholars to study world science and do great things. After all, as our grandfather Navoi used to say, "He who knows the language knows the world."

Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. This does not exclude the process of preschool education. The importance of teaching foreign languages during youth education has increased significantly. Natalya Kireeva, a religious scientist, candidate of historical sciences, senior teacher, said: "Either we prepare for life or for exams. We choose the first one." he emphasized. Recently, he spoke about the local education system and principles, and shared his thoughts on why Finnish education is considered one of the best in the world. Nowadays, paying attention to preschool education means social, economic and spiritual development of the state. Emphasizing that

To help you succeed, we're asking preschool experts to share their favorite early childhood teaching strategies. This list of teaching strategies for the preschool age group provides excellent transition opportunities for growth and learning as an educator.

1. Method of working with characters and pictures. One way to promote everyday vocabulary is to "give children a verbal guide to common brands and symbols," says Dr. Elaine Fogel Schneider, director of Touchtime International. He explains that picture-to-word translation helps develop language. That is, it helps children learn new languages quickly and easily.

2. Voice recognition and matching method. For this activity, you will need several large letters cut out of cardboard and several small, but not too large, things that begin with these letters.

For example, if your letters are M and K, and you have a cat and an elephant. Begin by telling the child the sound a cat makes. Then, encourage the child to find something that starts with the same sound and stick it to the letter. Decorated letters can be kept in the classroom or taken home to share with parents. Schneider said the activity is a favorite among students because it gives them a hands-on approach to learning. In addition, it creates a "masterpiece".

3. A way to get used to the natural world. Children are very interested in learning lessons in the natural environment. Usually, a backyard garden can be a great way to educate them about the natural world. This method of growing a plant from seed to maturity is important not only for children to learn about their growth, but also for them to quickly and easily learn words in a foreign language. This method relieves stress and helps improve fine motor skills.

4. The method of adapting one's activity to students. It can be easy to fall back on the teacher's manual or regular lessons you memorized in kindergarten. However, for some children, this causes problems. Gretzinger says children should be sensitive to children in non-traditional home environments. Think twice before asking students to draw pictures of their families - think about how an adopted or estranged child might feel and how other children might react need Inclusive activities can take a little longer, especially at the beginning of the year when you may not know all of your students, but a child's sense of embarrassment is known when you keep the mess. In this, the educator should continue his creativity. Pre-school education is the first stage of education and upbringing of our youth.

The right preschool program should help our children grow and learn in ways that match their unique intelligence. But children, unlike adults, do not learn thinking about the future, tomorrow. The English lesson should be held in the sense of "right here and right now". Children

learn a foreign language more easily by understanding stories or winning games. If they want, they can consolidate the information they have learned through games with their participation. On the one hand, the content expressed in language should be related to children's life and daily life, on the other hand, activities or tasks that engage children in communication should be interesting and important. During the lesson, students understand themselves as a part of the lesson and behave and act like the characters of the play during the lesson. In elementary grades, foreign language learning is usually very effective and successful when it is learned using action methods based on life situations and games. If a foreign language is taught through game-plot situations, all children will participate willingly, because in this way they feel that they are a part of that situation. Students "live" with a foreign language, first of all, in their classrooms.

Therefore, if it is possible to communicate in the classroom, it should be in that foreign language. Children can not only understand instructions, but also express their needs using a foreign language. In this regard, it is useful to communicate with English-speaking people (native English speakers) and invite them to the class. According to the constructive approach, children should learn the meaning of words and rules in as many languages as possible. It also helps them develop their basic thinking skills. Like all learners, children have different learning styles. Talim for children takes into account all styles of talim. Tactic and kinesthetic types of learning require special attention from the student. Pupils' talents, skills, knowledge and interests are wider in primary schools. Learning a foreign language also depends on the learner's ability to understand well. During the teaching of a foreign language, it is necessary to encourage each child for his actions. They should develop acoustic, kinesthetic, rhythmic and visual differentiation.

Children learn quickly, but forget quickly. Therefore, it is possible to help children remember the speech by repeating it several times and using games or handouts on this topic.

Courses are spiral, and regular repetitions are an integral part. Successful teaching of foreign languages requires comprehensive methods. The quantity and quality of communication are the main reasons for faster language learning. During the lesson, students' attention should be focused mainly on the content and importance of the language.

Students should first focus on the content of the language. Successful teaching of foreign languages also depends on how skillfully the teacher uses the opportunities available to him. Pupils should be given such tasks so that they are forced to apply and retain the knowledge they have learned during the lesson. Communication opportunities are important in the development of language skills. Social interaction, especially when students are able to apply the meaning of the language, enables them to use the language effectively. The teacher's ability to communicate and negotiate for this process is one of the main conditions for successful teaching.

Foreign language education should, first of all, focus on the study of everyday, real knowledge and contexts of a foreign language, but the development of specific knowledge should not be neglected. If we dwell on the methodical and didactic views used in the teaching of a foreign language, we need to emphasize the following: The teaching process is not only communicative, but it is necessary to include competences that give the opportunity to use the knowledge learned in the future. Many children are interested in learning foreign languages. Their interest is definitely related to the organization of the lesson process and the children's ability to achieve certain success in this lesson process. It is wrong to believe that this interest will remain the same throughout the

years, therefore, pedagogues need to take care of it, that is, ensure that students participate in the lesson with joy and success. The content and purpose of the lesson will be understandable and memorable to the students only if the topics being studied, as well as the questions, are important, interesting and relevant for the students. Foreign language learners encounter another language and culture in foreign language education. For this reason, it is recommended to use reliable materials specific to that foreign language, texts and texts that can convey that culture.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that the role of preschool education is important for our children to become adults. We need to provide them with modern technologies and modern education system. Pre-school education is of great importance for the development of the roots of every person in the society, that is, for them to grow up as children worthy of their motherland and strong individuals in the future. We need to pay more attention to the education of our children, create modern conditions, and help them learn using new methods. Learning foreign languages is also important for children to open the door to new opportunities in the future, for them to become qualified personnel, and for them to mature into a person who is beneficial to the whole society.

That is why we teach our children from a young age, make them interested in reading, do not forget every child in our society, deal with children who have difficulty learning, draw their attention with various interesting games, learn foreign languages. It is not wrong to say that our regular encouragement during training is the first step for their future education.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2012 yil 10 dekabrda "Chet tillarini o'rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida" gi PQ -1875-sonli qarori.
2. Iriskulov A.T va boshqalar; Kids' English pupil's book 2-sinf -Toshkent - O'zbekiston ; 2014
3. Passov Ye.I. Kommunikativniy metod obucheniya inoyazichnomu govoreniyu . M.: Prosveshenie, 1991
4. Xoshimov O'. Yoqubov I. Ingliz tili O'qitish metodikasi. T., -2003
5. Vyatyutnev M.N . Obuchenie inostrannomu yaziku v nachalnoy shkole. /inostranniy yazik v shkole , 1990.
6. Буриева Н. Г. Using songs and music in teaching English to young learners // Молодой ученый_ 2017
7. Krashen, Stephen D. and Terrel, Tracy. D. (1983). The natural approach. New Jersey: Alemany Press Regent / Prentice Hall.
8. Phillips S. (1993) Young learners. Oxford. England: Oxford University Press. Griffe, D. (1992) Songs in actions: Classroom techniques and resources. New York. Prentice Hall.